

APPLICATION OF THE EMBEDDED ELEMENT TECHNIQUE TO THE MODELLING OF NANO-ENGINEERED FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The Embedded Element (EE) technique is applied to model fiber-reinforced composites with carbon nanotubes (CNTs). The technique is based on the interaction of independently created finite element meshes linked to each other by multi-point constraints. Its advantages and limitations for micro-stress analysis in nano-reinforced composites are discussed. To further implement debonding of nanotubes from the matrix, the EE technique is to be combined with the cohesive elements approach. For this a thin layer of matrix is first inserted around the nanotubes. To verify the proposed approach, interfacial shear stresses in the EE models are compared with those in full finite element models for the case of a single straight nanotube. Our results indicate that the embedded element technique provides an attractive combination of computational cost and flexibility to model nano-engineered composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

There is experimental evidence that carbon nanotubes (CNTs) improve damage resistance of fiber reinforced polymer composites [1], [2]. To better understand mechanisms behind this improvement we recently developed a versatile two-scale model that is capable to predict stress distribution in CNT modified composites [3], [4], [6]. It is based on the embedded element technique for the finite element analysis [5], [6]. With this model, different CNT configurations can be generated, including CNTs dispersed in the matrix and CNTs deposited on fibers with different alignment and orientation (Fig. 1). Complex network-like configurations can also be considered. Up to now this model has provided new insights into the effect of CNTs on stresses in a composite prior to the onset of damage, but it has been limited to elastic stresses. Additionally, nanotubes have been modelled as solid cylindrical bodies.

Figure 1: A 3D unit cell of a UD carbon fiber composite with different CNT assemblies: (a) uniformly dispersed CNTs in the matrix; (b) agglomerated CNTs; (c) random CNT forest and (d) radially aligned CNT forest on fibers [6].

The current work aims to further advance the model towards a more realistic representation of nanotubes and to the prediction of damage. Here CNTs are modeled as hollow cylinders meshed with shell elements. An interphase layer around nanotubes is introduced as a step to include CNT debonding. The latter is to be modeled by combining the EE method and the cohesive elements approach. The mesh representing a nanotube with an interface layer is embedded in the matrix mesh, and cohesive elements are placed on the surface of the nanotube. Implementation of this approach, first, asks for validation of the EE model for the case of an embedded zone consisting of a nanotube and an interface layer. The paper provides this validation, opening a way to model nano- and micro damage in composites.

2 EE TECHNIQUE: ADVANTAGES AND LIMITATIONS

As the name of the Embedded Element method implies, one region of a Finite Element (FE) model is embedded into another region. The essence of the EE method, when applying it to CNT reinforced composites, is schematically shown in Fig.2, where the embedded region – an individual CNT – is embedded into the host region – the matrix. First, solid geometry of the matrix is created. Then, geometry of the CNT region is generated within the region of the matrix. The corresponding volume of the CNT is not extracted from the matrix region leaving the latter with the untouched or “non-degenerated” geometry. Then, the FE meshes of both these regions are created independently from each other. In this way, elements of CNTs and matrix do not share the same nodes making these FE meshes non-continuous.

Figure 2: (a) a schematic with the EE technique principle; (b) a model with independent FE meshes of CNTs and the matrix. All entities are meshed with 3D solid elements.

The FE mesh of an individual CNT is linked to the matrix mesh with an internal procedure performed by Abaqus. For every node of a given CNT the closest matrix element face is defined. The latter is marked with solid edges on the schematic in Fig. 2a. Then, all degrees of freedom (DOF) at the given CNT node are constrained to the matrix element face via equations expressing equality of interpolated displacements. This is done with appropriate weight factors internally calculated by Abaqus and determined based on the geometric location of the given CNT node in the matrix element. In other words, the given CNT node becomes constrained by the response of the host matrix element and vice versa. By such a procedure, additional mass and stiffness of each CNT is introduced into the model.

The EE technique possesses the following limitations [7]:

1. Only translational DOF at an embedded node are constrained. Rotational, temperature, electrical potential etc. DOF are not constrained.
2. Host elements should not be smaller than the embedded elements.
3. The material defined for the host element is not replaced by the material defined for the embedded element at the same location of the integration point.

The second limitation comes from the very principle of assigning the displacement constraints: every CNT node is constrained to its closest matrix element face. If host matrix elements are smaller than CNT elements, there might be some matrix elements along the CNT that are not constrained. On contrary, in the case when host matrix elements are larger than CNT elements, all matrix elements

along the CNT are assigned and constrained to the CNT nodes. A single matrix element may be assigned to several CNT nodes that happen to lie close to it. In this case, CNT nodes are constrained independently from each other multiplying the reinforcement effect in this matrix element. Although, the best scenario is the size equality of matrix elements and CNT elements, this is hardly realizable in models containing thousands of CNTs. The computational efficiency would have been very low, due to an enormous number of elements required. The mesh verification study shown further will determine an appropriate relation between sizes of matrix and CNT elements.

The third limitation is common for most non-continuous meshing methods. These inevitably face a problem of the doubling of the volume occupied by the reinforcing material. Being non-degenerated, the host domain of the matrix occupies this volume as well. Consequently, a redundant mass and stiffness of the matrix material is introduced into the model. This becomes a very critical point for the cases of reinforcements with a high volume fraction. When inserting an interphase layer with polymer properties around a nanotube, the doubling of the volume should be taken into account. Since the longitudinal modulus of CNTs is higher than the one of the matrix by two orders of magnitude, the contribution of the corresponding redundant matrix mass and stiffness to the stress distribution in the composite can be neglected.

One of the most appealing advantages of the EE technique is the nondegenerated host (matrix) domain geometry. This allows creation of well-structured meshes of all constituents – the matrix, the fibers and CNTs – using, for instance, the sweep technique. The swept mesh with a good structure drastically decreases the FE mesh complexity in comparison with the direct geometry implementation (DGI). This significantly enhances the numerical efficiency of the model by means of both the required number of elements - hence, calculation time – and overall quality of the mesh, therefore – calculation accuracy.

In order to understand whether the EE technique is suitable for FE modeling of CNTs in the matrix, it was validated on the example of a single CNT. Once validated, it can be applied to a full-scale model with thousands of CNTs. The aim of this study is to verify the EE technique solution against the solution obtained with a continuous mesh using a classical FE approach when CNTs and matrix are meshed together.

3 A SINGLE NANOTUBE EMBEDDED INTO THE MATRIX

A single straight CNT of a finite length was embedded into the matrix and analysed under longitudinal loading using the FE method. Several configurations were considered, which were characterised by different ways of CNT discretisation. In the first case, called “EE Solid model”, the nanotube was considered as a solid cylinder with a length of 700 nm, a radius, r , of 9 nm and meshed with 8-node solid bricks (C3D8). In the second case, called “EE Shell model”, the nanotube geometry was a hollow cylinder with a wall thickness of 3.5 nm and the same length and radius. This roughly corresponds to a multi-wall carbon nanotube (MWCNT) with 10 walls. General-purpose conventional shell elements (S4) were chosen for the discretisation where the outer surface of the nanotube was used as the reference surface. In both cases the matrix was meshed with 8-node brick elements (C3D8). For the superposition models multi-point constraints were used to embed the CNT in the matrix mesh, referenced to as host matrix. The translational degrees of freedom of the embedded nodes were constrained to the interpolated values of the corresponding degrees of freedom of the appropriate host elements, whereas the rotational degrees of freedom of the shell elements were not constrained by the embedding. In addition, full 3D FE solid models with conventionally meshed phases were created for providing a reference solution. Solid and shell elements were used to discretize nanotubes in full models correspondingly to the case studies, referred to as “Full Solid model” and “Full Shell model”.

Linear elastic behavior was assumed for all phases. The CNT was modelled as anisotropic solids with properties given in Table 1. When using shell elements for the hollow nanotube, an appropriate mapping to calculate the longitudinal Young's modulus was done depending on the cross-section (Fig. 3). Remaining engineering constants were kept the same. The polymer considered in the present work was epoxy with a Young's modulus of 3.0 GPa and a Poisson's ratio of 0.4.

Figure 3: Mapping longitudinal Young's modulus between solid and hollow CNTs. Other engineering constants are kept the same.

Engineering constant	Identification	Engineering constant	Identification
Nanotube (hollow cross-section)		Matrix	
E_1	[GPa] 525	E	[GPa] 3
$E_2 = E_3$	[GPa] 10.3	ν	- 0.4
$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	- 0.3		
ν_{23}	- 0.36		
$G_{12} = G_{13}$	[GPa] 27.9		
G_{23}	- 3.8		

Table 1: Elastic properties of the CNTs and epoxy matrix.

For the purpose of determining interfacial shear stresses in the matrix, the nanotube was placed in the middle of a parallelepiped-shaped matrix volume with a length, width and height equal to 1400, 140 and 140 nm, respectively. Strain of 0.3% in the longitudinal direction was applied on the faces perpendicular to the nanotube direction. The other remaining faces were subjected to symmetry boundary conditions.

Special attention was paid to the meshing procedure, as results showed strong dependencies on the quality of the mesh, namely the appropriate number and type of elements. To have a reliable reference model, the mesh around the nanotube/matrix interface and near the ends of the nanotube in the full FE models was refined. First, an additional partition of the volume element was carried out: a circular layer with radius of 9 units was added around the nanotube, where one unit length corresponds to one nanometer. 32 elements along the circumference resulted in an average element size of $2 \cdot \pi \cdot r / 32$, which is approximately 0.88 units for the nanotube and interface. Second, additional seeds in the area around the nanotube ends were placed. The length of the corresponding hex elements was 1.25 units around the ends of the nanotube and 10 units in the remaining area. Similar element sizes for the matrix and nanotube were applied in the embedded models. As will be shown later, such a fine mesh for an embedded model leads to accurate results, but one should keep in mind, that this approach will be applied on larger volume elements. If we consider as an example a matrix cube of $2 \times 2 \times 2 \mu\text{m}^3$ using a matrix element size of 2 nm, we would obtain a model with 10^9 elements. Thus it is essential to investigate the influence of rough meshes and to understand accuracy of the embedded element technique.

For embedded models several mesh sizes were considered for the nanotube: global element size was equal to $0.2r$, $0.4r$ and $0.8r$ length units, respectively, along the length and at the circumference, where r is the outer radius of the nanotube. For each case, a matrix mesh size was chosen which was 2x and 4x bigger compared to the nanotube mesh. Different mesh cases for the "EE Solid model" are shown in Fig.4, the same mesh sizes were chosen for the "EE Shell model".

Figure 4: Different mesh cases shown for the “EE Solid model”

Interfacial shear stresses should be taken from the interface between the nanotube and the matrix. In the case of the embedded model, however, such an interface is not clearly defined due to the mesh differences mismatch between nanotubes and matrix. Values for interfacial stresses in the matrix were, therefore, taken from elements which were closest to the nanotube, but not intersecting with it (Fig. 5). Stresses were interpolated from the integration points.

Figure 5: Element path (in red) defining the interface between the matrix and the nanotube in the EE model

Interfacial shear stresses for the “Full Shell” and the “EE Shell model” (with different mesh sizes) are presented in (Fig. 6a). It can be observed that the shear stresses are more sensitive to the matrix mesh than to the nanotube mesh. Increasing the matrix mesh 8 times, the maximum shear stresses around the nanotube end decreased by 87%. Interfacial shear stresses for the “Full Solid” and “EE Solid model” have similar values and are not presented here.

The influence of nanotube anisotropy was investigated in comparison with isotropic formulation. The isotropic nanotube was modelled with Young’s modulus of 525 GPa for the “Shell model” and

500 GPa for the “Solid model”, Poisson’s ratio of 0.4 for both models. Relative errors in the interfacial shear stress between the “EE Shell” and “Full Shell model” and between “EE Solid” and “Full Solid model” are presented in Fig.6b. Minor differences between isotropic and anisotropic cases are observed. Anisotropic “EE Shell” and “EE Solid” models show slightly better results in comparison with the isotropic “EE Solid” model.

Figure 6: (a) Interfacial shear stresses (EE shell model with anisotropic nanotube); (b) comparison of “EE solid” and “EE shell models” with the corresponding “Full models” for isotropic and anisotropic nanotubes.

3 ADDITION OF THE INTERPHASE LAYER

To simulate the decohesion mechanism at the CNT/matrix interface, cohesive forces that exist in the fracture process zone should be taken into account. So-called cohesive-zone models (CZM) are considered as one of the most commonly used tools to investigate interfacial fracture [8], [9]. In case of the fiber/matrix interphase the “adhesive layer” is placed between the fiber and matrix, where the matrix and fiber are meshed separately. The stress state between the cohesive surfaces can be defined in the interaction module in Abaqus /CAE according to certain material softening law, which is called a cohesive law or traction-separation law. In the case of the nanotube/matrix interphase, one could do the same as for the fiber, but in the presence of thousands of nanotubes this approach would simply become not feasible. Therefore, nanotubes and matrix are meshed independently and linked to each other using the EE model. The previous results show that this technique is very attractive due to a combination of low computational costs and flexibility and can give quite accurate results with an appropriately chosen mesh. But the interface between nanotube and matrix is no longer defined as a surface. To make the simulation of CNT/matrix debonding possible, a thin layer is inserted around the nanotube. The nanotube and the interphase layer are thereafter embedded into the matrix. To validate this model, mesh sensitivity analysis is performed and comparison is done against the full FE model.

An anisotropic hollow tube meshed with shell elements and embedded into matrix is further investigated as it showed the best agreement with the full model. The nanotube with an interphase layer was embedded into the matrix. Such superposition leads to the doubling of the volume in the reinforcement and interphase zones. To eliminate the excessed stiffness, the heuristic “shortcut” approach was followed as proposed in [10]. The stiffness in the interphase layer was set to zero (1MPa to avoid numerical errors) and the corresponding interfacial strain was calculated. As stresses in the interphase region, also called *slave matrix*, are now in a wrong relation to the strains, the stresses should be recalculated with respect to the true stiffness.

$$\sigma = C^{true} \varepsilon^{corrected} \quad (1)$$

where σ denotes the recalculated stresses in the interphase region, C^{true} is the true stiffness tensor for the matrix and $\varepsilon^{corrected}$ the calculated strain with the corrected stiffness.

Consequently the final interfacial shear stress takes the form of:

$$\sigma_{12} = \frac{E^{true}}{1+\nu} \varepsilon_{12}^{corrected} \quad (2)$$

As aforementioned the maximum interfacial shear stresses occur in the element set in close proximity to the nanotube elements and not intersecting with them. This means that to have maximum shear stresses within the interphase layer its thickness has to be equal or larger than the global element size in the matrix (Fig. 7). If the interphase layer is too thin, than the maximum shear stresses occur outside this region (see Fig.7, where slave matrix and host matrix are depicted in the longitudinal cross section without nanotube).

(a)

(b)

Figure 7: Processing of the results. (a) interfacial shear stress in the host matrix in EE Shell model with an interphase; (b) definition of the interphase thickness depending on the matrix element size

Interfacial shear strains were computed along the interphase path in the slave as well as in the host matrix. A comparison of the recalculated interfacial stresses is presented in Fig. 8a. The “fine mesh” corresponds to the nanotube mesh size of $0.2r$ and the matrix mesh size of $0.4r$ and the “coarse mesh” corresponds to mesh sizes of $0.8r$ and $3.2r$, respectively. As no distinct difference can be observed, it was concluded that the introduction of an interphase layer in embedded models is not negatively affecting the calculation of interfacial stresses.

Recalculated stresses for different embedded Shell models with interphase layer and a Full Shell model are presented in Fig.8b. The thickness of the interphase layer was selected in correspondence to the matrix mesh size. It can be seen from Fig. 8b that models with a coarse mesh underestimate the interfacial stresses obtained in the full Shell model and the finer the mesh the better coincide the stress results.

Figure 8: (a) Interfacial shear stresses in host and slave matrix; (b) ISS in embedded model with reduced stiffness of the interphase layer, calculated in the embedded elements of the interphase.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Due to computational requirements and meshing efforts, the use of conventional full 3D Solid models is a challenging task to simulate mechanical behavior of composites reinforced by CNTs. An embedded element model is proposed to model nanotubes embedded into a polymer matrix. In this case the nanotubes are meshed separately from the matrix using solid or shell elements and then superimposed with the matrix. The relative difference in the interfacial shear stresses predicted by conventional full models and embedded shell/solid models is slightly higher for the solid model.

An accurate prediction of damage onset and propagation in such composites is even more challenging, as debonding of nanotubes from the matrix has to be considered. To implement this phenomenon in the model, an additional layer with polymer properties is inserted around a nanotube and embedded in the host matrix. The thickness of this layer has to be equal or larger than the global elements size of the matrix. If the interphase layer is too thin, than maximum shear stresses lie outside of this layer. To count for the “doubled” volume in the superimposed models a stiffness correction in the redundant interphase layer was applied. Results were compared with calculations obtained with conventional full models. For all models, maximum interfacial shear stresses occurred near the ends of the nanotubes. It was observed that interfacial shear stresses were much more sensitive to mesh refining in the matrix rather than in the nanotube.

Despite very strong mesh sensitivity, embedded models with an extra matrix layer around a nanotube (meshed with shell elements) appear to be a promising approach for modeling of damage in nano-engineered composites. Future work will focus on the effects of CNT debonding on composite toughness.

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